

SPACE ASTROMETRY

On-board data handling: IDT piloting and acquisition of scientific data

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1. Introduction

The tasks of the data handling on board HIPPARCOS may be summarized under the headings:

- a, Acquisition and pre-processing of scientific data from IDT
- b, Acquisition and pre-processing of scientific data from star mapper
- c, IDT piloting.
- d, Real-time attitude determination
- e, Attitude control
- f, Thermal control.

This note is concerned with items a) - c).

Item b, may need some clarification. The star mapper is the only source of information about the full three-axes attitude over long periods of time. The data from the star mapper is used for two different purposes:

- 1) for calibrating the gyros, yielding the approximate ($\pm 1''$) ^{real-time} attitude knowledge needed for tasks c) - e), and

2, for obtaining in the final reductions an attitude determination to about $\pm 0.1''$, which is needed in all three axes in order to secure the 1 milliarcsec accuracy of angles along the scans.

Thus, although observation of perhaps 10-20 bright stars is sufficient for the first purpose, it may be necessary to observe many more stars (perhaps 100-200?) with the star mapper for the second purpose.

Therefore, we should distinguish between the collection and preprocessing (compression) of star-mapper data on one hand (task b), and on the other the ~~the~~ further processing of a subset of these data for the real-time attitude determination. (~~task~~ part of task d).

2. Nominal data for instrument and mission

We consider here a telescope with two rectangular apertures, 250×125 cm, a field of view (FOV) of $54' \times 54'$ for the IDT and $20' \times 54'$ for the star mapper. Cathode material is S20. From this we derive the following preliminary data:

- grid period $s = 1.0''$
- ratio (clear band)/(period) $\delta = 0.23$
- modulation of expected count rate:

$$I(x) = I_0 [1 + a_1 \cos(2\pi x/s) + a_2 \cos(4\pi x/s) + a_3 \cos(6\pi x/s)] \text{ counts/sec.}$$

where

$$I_0 \approx 10^{7.2 - 0.4B} \text{ counts/sec} \quad (B = \text{blue star magnitude})$$

$$a_1 \approx 0.55$$

$$a_2 \approx 0.20$$

$$a_3 \approx 0.00$$

Hence, the maximum count rate expected for a star of blue magnitude B is $1.75 \cdot 10^{7.2 - 0.4B}$ counts/sec.

The only mission parameter of immediate interest is the nominal spin rate, taken to be $150''/\text{sec}$ ($R=10$).

3. Acquisition of scientific data : sampling rate and compression

It is assumed that photon-counting techniques are used for both JDT and star mapper photomultiplier tube (PMT). Thus, the output pulses (each roughly corresponding to a detected photon) are counted in consecutive, equal, and fixed intervals of time, each of length Δt (sampling period). Between adjacent intervals there is no loss of time.

Our first objective should be to fix the sampling rate $1/\Delta t$, since we shall in fact build the whole observation strategy as a hierarchy with integer multiples of Δt (mostly "nice" integers in the binary system) at the different levels. The following considerations apply:

1. If little or no data compression is used, the down-link data rate is almost proportional to the sampling rate, which should therefore not be unnecessarily high.
2. On the other hand, too low a sampling rate will increase the stochastic errors of the positions derived from the counts, mainly because of the reduction of modulation (by a factor $\sin(\pi f \Delta t) / (\pi f \Delta t)$ for modulation frequency f) of the signal integrated over the finite interval Δt .
3. It is probably of some advantage to have (at least roughly) some

integer number of samples per fundamental signal modulation period; in that case we prefer (say) 4, 8, 12 or 16 samples per modulation period, in order to preserve certain symmetries in time.

From the nominal data in Section 2 it follows that the fundamental signal modulation frequency (period corresponding to grid period) is 150 Hz. In fact, since $a_2 \neq 0$ but $a_3 = 0$ we should have, according to the sampling theorem, $\Delta t^{-1} > 600$ Hz. A computation of the degradation of accuracy with decreasing sampling rate was done for the circular pupil (and $s = 1.2$) in (Lindgren, Note 79-02-20). Re-scaling to $s = 1$ ", we conclude that $\Delta t^{-1} = 600$ Hz would give about 20% increase of m.e. (Compared with infinite sampling rate), whereas $\Delta t^{-1} = 1200$ Hz would increase m.e. by 4%. The latter figure is quite acceptable, and would give exactly 8 samples per signal period. Since most counts will fit well into one 8-bit word each, we get a down-link data rate for this purpose of 9.6 kbits/sec.

We assume $\Delta t = 1/1200$ sec.

Moreover, we shall assume that this sampling rate is absolutely fixed (e.g. by on-board quartz clock) rather than tunable and locked to the signal modulation frequency (nominally 150 Hz). This appears to be the simpler alternative and should give same accuracy of final results at the expense of a slightly more sophisticated software for the final reductions.

Data compression. Since 9.6 kbits/sec seems to be quite an acceptable data rate, there is no direct need for compression

as long as the number of counts per Δt is less than 256. With $\Delta t = 1/1200$ sec and allowing a 3σ spread of counts, we find the limiting magnitude $B = 5.1$. Only a few percent of the stars to be observed are brighter and require either more bits per sample or some data compression.

Logarithmic coding (with 5 bit mantissa and 3 bit exponent) can code all counts from 256 to $\sim 32'000$ with relative rounding error between $\pm \frac{1}{128}$ and $\pm \frac{1}{64}$. 32'000 counts corresponds to $B = -0.1$ and a count rate of 39 MHz, which is probably much more than the IDT, amplifier/discriminator and counter can take anyway. Relative accuracy $\pm 1/64$ is probably sufficient in view of cathode inhomogeneities etc.

Therefore, 8 bits/sample is probably always sufficient. In fact, the median magnitude of the stars is about $B = 8.6$, corresponding to maximum 17 counts (3σ), for which 5 bits is definitely sufficient. This allows the average IDT data rate to be compressed to ≤ 7.8 kbits/sec, without loss of resolution; this may be sufficient to overcome limitations of data links on ground.

Acquisition of data from star mapper

Since the resolution of the telescope and the spin rate are the same for the star mapper as for the IDT, I can see no reason for selecting a different (lower) sampling frequency for the star mapper than for the IDT (Aeritalia proposes $\Delta t^{-1} = 198$ Hz, Vol. II p. 259), apart from the proportional reduction of computations.

However, provided that the true spin rate can be kept very close to the nominal 150"/sec (this probably requires "active" rather than "intermittent" attitude control), and provided that the star mapper grid period is a multiple of Δt , we can lump together the counts at equal phases before computing the Fourier transform. This reduces the number of multiplications by a factor equal to the number of grid periods in the observed interval. With ~~30~~ ^{$\nu=3$} for the star mapper we end up with 24 multiplications (this can be reduced at least by a factor 2 more by subtracting samples at $\approx 180^\circ$ phase difference).

Such coherent lumping-together of samples is probably acceptable also for star mapper observations intended only for use in final reductions. But the FT may be too crude here, since it destroys information on parasitic stars which are much more important for the star mapper than for the IDT, where they are ^{mostly} removed by the cathode spot.

4. IDT piloting

The piloting of the IFOV [i.e. the deflection coil currents as functions of time: $i_x(t), i_y(t)$] is determined by the on-board computer, using information from four sources:

1. A short catalogue on board, containing approximate ($\sim 1''$) positions, magnitudes ($\pm 0.25^m$) and priorities (a few bits) of stars which may be observed during the next few minutes.

The catalogue is regularly updated from the ground.

2. The real-time attitude determination (to $\pm 1''$), provided by the gyros (in turn calibrated with star mapper observations).

3. A look-up table on board with corrections to i_x and i_y (as functions of x, y) deriving from misalignments, optical and electronic distortions, etc. If possible, this table should guarantee a residual distortion $< \pm 1''$ without the need of interpolation.

4. The detailed piloting scheme (when to switch between which stars) is not up-linked but is determined by a program on board. A possible program is outlined below.

It is assumed that, given the position of a star, the attitude knowledge, and the look-up table ~~for~~ for the distortions, it is possible to compute (i_x, i_y) to sufficient accuracy (corresponding to a $\pm 2''$ error on photocathode) well in advance (say, 1 sec before the

star is actually there). Four such computations are needed for every switch period (≈ 0.2 sec); if distortions are smoothed enough two computations per 0.2 sec may be sufficient.

Time hierarchy

The elementary time interval is the sampling period $\Delta t \approx 0.83$ ms.

Since the modulation period nominally corresponds to $8\Delta t$, we let the IFOV dwell on one and the same star uninterrupted for a multiple of $8\Delta t$; or rather:

dwell time = $(8n - 1) \Delta t$, $n = 2, 3, 4, \dots, 29, 30$.
(subobservation)

The integer n will depend on the brightness of the star. The term -1 comes from the sample being lost while the IFOV is originally positioned on the star (i.e. switched from another star to this one).

After having observed star A during $8n_A - 1$ samples, the IFOV is switched to another star B (whereby one sample is again lost), which is then observed for $8n_B - 1$ samples. Then IFOV switches back to A, and so on. The integers n_A and n_B are chosen so that

$n_A + n_B = 32$.

The total time spent on A and B (including switching) ^{before returning to A} is then $8 \cdot 32 \Delta t = 256 \Delta t \approx 0.213$ sec. This is the switch period.

It is convenient to introduce still one higher level of this

Figure 1

Hierarchy of observations

A, B, and C show the beginning (from $t=0$) of the same observation with decreasing resolution

Continuous motion of IFOV (constant speed k, y)

$(n_A = 12, n_B = 20)$

$(n_B = 16, n_C = 16)$

$(n_B = 21, n_D = 11)$

(...)

hierarchy: one ~~an~~ observation cycle containing always 8 switch periods, i.e. switching back and forth 8 times between the same two stars A and B. Thus one obs. cycle = $2048 \Delta t \approx 1.707 \text{ sec.}$

The next cycle may be concerned with the same pair of stars (A+B), a completely different pair (C+D), or a partly different pair of stars, (A+C) or (B+C).

It would make things a little bit easier ~~if~~ if n was fixed once and for all (i.e. $n=16$ for symmetry reasons), but this would result in some loss of accuracy when observing pairs with a large magnitude difference. The brighter star ~~will~~ should of course receive shorter time ($n < 16$) than the fainter star ($n > 16$). The optimum partitioning of $n_A + n_B$ is derived in Appendix 2. It is found that n_A is mainly a function of the magnitude difference $m_A - m_B$ and can be obtained from a simple look-up table. (This is the main reason why approximate magnitudes must be given in the star catalogue.)

With this scheme, the observation strategy reduces to the problem of selecting, for each new cycle (every 1.707 sec), the two stars which ought to be observed in that cycle.

This selection procedure should take into account:

- which stars are in the FOV for the entire cycle,
- the different priorities of different stars,
- that we might prefer to connect pairs where the two stars come from different FOV's (p or f),

- that as many different pairs as possible should be observed (because redundancy is security), and finally
- that the observations should be well distributed in the FOV. In particular, an asymmetric distribution along the scanning direction should be avoided, because that might enhance systematic errors (chromaticity etc.).

Star catalogue

The short star catalogue on board should list the stars to be observed for at least the next 25 sec. The following data are needed for each star: (i = star number)

t_i = time of entrance (i.e. the ~~time~~ time the star enters the IDT FOV, reckoned from some arbitrary origin). Since an accuracy of $\pm 0.5''$ is sufficient (resolution = $1''$), t_i may be expressed in units of $8\Delta t = 6.67 \text{ ms} \Leftrightarrow 1''$. 16 bits then corresponds to 436 sec or 7.3 min or 18.2° , which is more than sufficient to avoid confusion over the arc of $\approx 2^\circ$ which we are working with at a certain time.

h_i = the height of the star in the FOV. With $1''$ resolution, the field of $54'$ + tolerances requires at least 12 bits.

m_i = approximate magnitude. Resolution 0.5 magn and interval 0 - 15.5 magn. $\Rightarrow$ 5 bits required.

p_i = priority. Here we assume $p_i = 0, 1, 2, \text{ or } 3 \Rightarrow$ 2 bits required.

v_i = this indicates which FOV (preceding, p, or following, f) the star belongs to. Ex. $v_i = 0$ for p, $v_i = 1$ for f. (1 bit)

q_i = this indicates the status of the star with respect to star-mapper observations. 2 bits required, e.g.:

$q_i = 0 \Rightarrow$ star shall not be observed with star mapper

$q_i = 1 \Rightarrow$ to be observed, but data not used for real-time att. determination

$q_i = 2 \Rightarrow$ star used for real-time att. det.

$q_i = 3$ (not used)

In total we need at least 38 bits per star; if we ~~take 38 bits~~ admit 3 16-bit words per star these may contain:

1st word: t_i

2nd word: h_i (4 bits left)

3rd word: m_i, p_i, v_i, q_i (6 bits left).

With attitude tolerances $\pm 10'$, we must store data for stars in a band of width $74' = 0.0215$ rad. Per degree (0.0175 rad) in the scanning direction we then have, on the average,

$$2 \times 10^5 \times \frac{0.0215 \times 0.0175 \text{ sterad}}{4\pi \text{ sterad}} \approx 6.0 \text{ stars/degree}$$

for an observing program with 10^5 stars. [Factor 2 comes from superpositioning of the two FOV's.]. Since the scan rate is $150''/\text{sec} = 1$ degree per 24 sec, we have to uplink star data at an average ~~rate~~ rate of 1 star per 4 sec. Thus the average bit-rate is 12 bits/sec.

The storage needed for the catalogue is limited by:

- minimum arc needed $\sim 2^\circ \Rightarrow 12$ stars on average;
- maximum arc with 16 bit resolution of $t_i \sim 18^\circ \Rightarrow \sim 110$ stars.

Of the order of 50 stars may be stored, which means that the catalogue must be updated at least every 3rd minute.

Notice that the time of disappearance from the IDT FOV is $t_i + 21.6 \text{ sec} = T_i$, but the star may still be used for the star mapper; thus, star i must not be deleted from the catalogue until time is $\geq t_i + 30 \text{ sec}$.

Observing strategy: selection of pair for each cycle ($2048 \Delta t \approx 1.7 \text{ sec}$)

Observation within one cycle is completely determined by:

- i_A and i_B , i.e. the two stars to be switched between, and
- m_A and m_B , i.e. the magnitudes of the stars, from which n_A and $n_B = 32 - n_A$ are derived.

Thus, on the cycle-to-cycle level, the only problem is to select the stars i_A and i_B . The following might be a useful strategy:

1. Let us number the cycles consecutively $j = 1, 2, \dots$, so that ~~the time~~ cycle j lasts from $t = 2048(j-1) \Delta t$ to $2048j \Delta t$. Since the time of entrance of star i is ~~$t = t_i \cdot 8 \Delta t$~~ $t = t_i \cdot 8 \Delta t$ and its time of disappearance is $t = t_i \cdot 8 \Delta t + 21.6 \text{ sec} = (t_i + 3240) \cdot 8 \Delta t$, we find that star i is observable in cycles $j_1(i) \leq j \leq j_2(i)$, where

$$j_1(i) = 2 + \text{entier}(t_i / 256)$$

$$j_2(i) = \text{entier}[(t_i + 3240) / 256] \quad (\text{see Fig.})$$

Fig. $j_1(i)$ and $j_2(i)$ are the first and last cycles in which star i may be observed (only complete cycles can be used).
 TOE = time of entrance, TOD = time of disappearance.

The numbers $j_1(i)$ and $j_2(i)$ ^{computed on board and} are stored in the catalogue.

2. ~~As soon as~~ As soon as star i has been added to the catalogue, we can see which pairs it may form with the previous stars, for which the numbers j_1 and j_2 are of course also available. The possible pairs are stacked in different queues in the same order as they are found. For simplicity, let us number the pairs $k=1, 2, \dots$. Given k for the last pair, the new pairs are found by a simple routine, e.g.:

The priority of the pair, Q , determines in which queue the pair should be put. If we admit eight queues, we may for instance compute $Q = 0 - 7$ (increasing priority) according to:

$$Q(k) = p_i + p_{i'} + \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } v_i \neq v_{i'} \text{ (different fields)} \\ 1 & \text{if } v_i = v_{i'} \text{ (same field)} \end{cases}$$

Since $0 \leq p_i \leq 3$ it follows that $0 \leq Q \leq 7$.

3. In the relevant queue, the following data should be available:

- ~~number of first star~~
- i = first star ~~()~~
- i' = second star ~~()~~
- $j_a(k)$ = the first cycle in which both i and i' are observable
- $j_b(k)$ = the last cycle " " " " " " " " " "
- f = this is a one-bit flag, to be explained below.

The position of a pair in the queues is given by the queue number Q and an index l . ~~At~~ At a certain time, queue Q may contain pairs in the range $\min(Q) \leq l \leq \max(Q)$.

~~A new pair is added to queue Q at index $l = \max(Q)$, whereupon $\max(Q)$ is incremented by one.~~

A new pair is added to queue Q at index $l = \max(Q)$, whereupon $\max(Q)$ is incremented by one.

A pair is deleted from queue Q by incrementing $\min(Q)$ by one (always, only the first pair in the queue can be deleted).

4. The flag f is used to indicate ($f=1$) that this pair was just observed; it causes a jump to the next pair in the same queue for the next observation cycle.

If the next pair is not observable in that cycle, one looks in the next queue (lower priority) for a pair.

If there is no pair in any of the queues, all flags are reset ($f=0$) and search begins again in the queue with highest priority.

) A flow diagram is given on next page.

If no pair can be observed in a particular cycle (with 3-4 stars in the FOV this should never happen), then we may observe one star instead of a pair during this cycle. This requires a special subroutine.

Example Fig 1: this shows the distribution of some 12 stars along the scan. The axis on top gives t_i = time of entrance. The possible pairs (arcs < 21.6 sec) are shown by horizontal bars; they are numbered 1-24. Also, the priorities p_i and field v_i are given (bottom). Note that $p_i = 2$ except $p_4 = 1$ and $p_6 = 3$.

Fig 2: this shows along a time axis the cycles $j=1, 2, \dots, 24$ and the visibility of the different pairs. It is seen, for instance, that pair # 7 is visible for cycles 13 - 17, i.e. $j_a(7) = 13$, $j_b(7) = 17$.

Fig. Selection of pair (i, i') for observation in cycle j.

Fig 3: this is how the 24 pairs are arranged in queues (only four queues are occupied). In each position, there are three numbers: pair#(k), $j_a(k)$ and $j_b(k)$. Thus 15 26-29 at top right means that pair 15 is visible for cycles $26 \leq j \leq 29$.

Fig 4: With the scheme on p. 16 the observations are ~~distributed~~ distributed among the pairs as indicated in Fig. 4. There are 4 pairs which escape observation: nr. 3 (which is impossible because too short), 5, 11, and 20.

Fig 6: This shows in a different way the resulting observation scheme: the paths of the stars across FOV and the pairs measured for each cycle.

FIG 1

FIG 2

Queues

increasing
l

Q = 7	2	3	4	5	6	Q = 7
		11 22-24	24 35-	23 32-	15 26-29	
		9 13-24	17 26-32	20 32-32	14 22-29	
			13 22-24	22 30-37	12 18-24	
			7 13-17	19 30-32		
			5 13-13	21 28-37		
			4 6-13	18 28-32		
				16 28-29		
				10 18-24		
				8 13-17		
				6 13-13		
				2 6-12		
				1 2-12		

FIG 4

FIG 6

$i =$
(star)

FIG 6